

Z-PINS TOPOLOGY DESIGN ON THE MODE I DELAMINATION OF Z-PINNED MULTI-LAYERED BIAXIAL WEFT KNITTED FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Mode I delamination tests are performed to characterise the strain energy release rate of the z-pinned composites reinforced by two MBWK fabric sheets, based on which analyses are developed, and finally a few strategies of the z-pins topology design are proposed, which may be beneficial to future engineering applications of such composites.

Keywords: Textile composites; Fracture toughness; Z-pins

INTRODUCTION

The multi-layered biaxial weft knitted (MBWK) fabrics composed of non-crimp glass insertion fibres (or other high performance fibres) and polyester stitch yarns, show superior conformability on curved surfaces [1] and their composites may serve as alternative materials to steels or other traditional engineering materials which can save energy and reduce emission. A feasible way to manufacture load-bearing structures with the MBWK fabrics can be found by means of sheet forming first and resin impregnation then via resin transfer moulding (RTM) or resin film infusion (RFI) techniques. This technical route requires much less energy than the metal sheet forming for two reasons, one of which is that the fabric can be formed to a given shape under very small load and without heating [1] and the other one of which is that resin is cured at a much lower temperature than that during the metal processing [2]. Furthermore, if the fabrics are processed as reinforcements to the main structures of the transportation vehicles, the emission is expected to be reduced than the metal structures on account of the higher specific modulus and strength and hence the lighter overall weight.

Although the MBWK fabrics can be knitted as the three dimensional reinforcements in factory, too thick fabrics may lose their superiority in formability to curved surfaces. Therefore the studied MBWK [1] is about 1.8 mm in thickness, which can be regarded as quasi-three dimensional reinforcement. Thinner fabrics will exhibit better formability owing to fewer interactions between neighbouring layers. However, the thru-thickness properties will be deteriorated in this case due to the absence of stitch yarns. Moreover, the stitch yarns cannot be too thick otherwise the space between the glass insertion yarns will be so wide that the rich resin area will be larger and reduce the composite properties more severely. Fortunately there are other techniques to improve the thru-thickness properties, e.g. z-pinning technique [3] which has drawn considerable attention and has got many advantages over other thru-thickness reinforcing techniques.

In this study, after deliberately evaluating above factors, two sheets of the present fabric are laminated with z-pins inserted through the thickness and then epoxy is impregnated via RFI technique to make the MBWK fabric/epoxy composite plate. Mode I delamination tests are conducted to characterise the interlaminar toughness of the two-sheet z-pinned composites. Z-pins improve the strain energy release rate G_{Ic} of the z-pinned composites by about 2.5 times over the no pins ones as have been reported by others [4,5]. However, the effect of z-pins topology [6] has not yet been as much studied as the z-pins volume fractions and diameters. So in this study the z-pins topology design based on the Mode I delamination tests is given.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The MBWK fabric (see detailed description in Ref. 1) is supplied by the Tianjin Polytechnic University. As the weft insertion yarns in both surface layers are made of 2×460 Tex GFs and more sparsely arranged than the interlayer warp ones which are made of 4×460 Tex GFs, both of the insertion yarns have the same thread count by 12 per inch and thus close volume fraction. Fabric parameters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters of the MBWK fabric.

Yarn	Volume fraction (%)	Material	Specification	Thread count (inch ⁻¹)
Weft insertion	47.1	E-glass fibre	460Tex×2	12
Warp insertion	49.4	E-glass fibre	460Tex×4	12
Stitch	3.5	PET DTY	150D×2	–

The thru-thickness reinforcement z-pins are made of carbon fibres CCF3002-3K-41 supplied by Weihai Tuo-Zhan Fibre Co., Ltd and epoxy matrix E51 supplied by Shanghai Ju-Xing Chemical Co. Ltd. E51 is a kind of general bisphenol-A epoxy resin which can be cured in room temperature with the amine modified epoxy hardener. The diameters of z-pins range from 0.28 to 0.51 mm, among which 0.51 mm z-pins are used in present study.

The epoxy matrix named VB-90 is supplied by the Beijing Institute of Aerospace Materials. VB-90 is resin film made of general bisphenol A epoxy, thermoplastic phenolphthalein resin modified polyether ketone (PEK-C) and curing agent tetrabromobisphenol A polycarbonate oligomer (BC).

Fig. 1. Z-pins topology and sample geometries for the Mode I delamination tests (a) regular matrix-like distribution (b) spatial topology pattern.

Fig. 2. Curing curve for the z-pinned composites.

The z-pinned laminate is fabricated via RFI technique. The stacking sequence on the aluminum molding plate is epoxy film, one MBWK fabric, the Teflon® film, from which an about 52 mm long pre-crack is initiated, and the other MBWK fabric. Z-pins are inserted into the fabric along the neighbouring space of the insertion yarns, with two kinds of z-pins topology, i.e. regular matrix-like distribution (RMD) and spatial topology pattern (STP) in Fig. 1. The uncured materials are sealed in the vacuum bag and cured in the oven following the curing curve in Fig. 2. In the end, the laminate is cooled down naturally in the oven. The samples of the Mode I delamination tests are double cantilever beams (DCB) cutting from the laminate as shown in Fig. 1. Piano hinges are affixed to the cracked edges of the samples that the initial crack length a_0 is about 50 mm. The thickness of the DCB samples is about 3.1 mm

Mode I Delamination Test

The Mode I fracture tests are performed following the ASTM standard D 5528-01. Both of the composite samples with and without z-pins are tested under a loading rate of $2\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ with an Instron® 3365 testing machine and at room temperature. A minimum of five coupons are tested for every group of materials. The crack length is measured with a Canon® digital camera.

The data reduction follows the modified beam theory (MBT) scheme as recommended in ASTM D 5528. The strain energy release rate G_{Ic} is calculated as below with the large displacement correction,

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3PD}{2B(a+|\Delta|)} F, F = 1 - \frac{3}{10} \left(\frac{D}{a} \right)^2 - \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{D \cdot t}{a^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where P and D are the applied force and corresponding displacement, B and a are the sample width and measured crack length, Δ is determined experimentally as the standard suggests, and t is the shape parameter for piano hinges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Load vs. arm-opening displacement and strain energy release rate vs. crack length curves are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. Because herein the distance between two neighbouring z-pins columns is about 11 to 12.5 mm, which is much bigger than that in the previous studies (2 to 3.5 mm) [4,7], some different phenomena are observed, for example when the five z-pins are all pulled out from the matrix the crack will propagate fast in the span of the two z-pins columns until the redundant energy is dissipated by the newly-born free surface or the crack tip is arrested by the next column of z-pins.

Samples without Z-Pins

The curves in Fig. 3 show zigzag phenomenon during the whole process of crack propagation, which is related to the microstructures of the MBWK fabric/epoxy composites. The existence of the stitch loops along the transverse direction hinders the crack propagation, which is similar to Cartié's photo [8] but caused by different mechanisms. As the applied load rises, the crack will climb over the stitch loops and propagate abruptly, as a result of which the load will fall down. This process can happen cyclically. As shown in Fig. 4, the strain energy releasing rate G_{Ic} of the sample without z-pins becomes constant when the crack length is larger than about 57 mm. The R Curve looks similar to the unidirectional composite laminates, from which it can be inferred

that the zigzag phenomenon does not intrinsically influence the fracture toughness of the composites, perhaps an increase or a decrease in value compared with their unidirectional counterparts. From Fig. 5, the transverse stitch loops can be seen clearly and no fibre bridging exists, although it is a familiar phenomenon for composite laminates without thru-thickness reinforcements.

Fig. 3. Load vs. displacement curves.

Fig. 4. Strain energy release rate vs. crack length.

Fig. 5. Wavy fracture path of samples without z-pins.

Samples Reinforced with Z-Pins

In Fig. 3, the initial linear part of the loading curves of z-pinned composites becomes steeper, which reflects the reinforcement of composites rigidity by the insertion of z-pins. And the critical load of crack extension is pronouncedly increased and so is stored strain energy. As soon as the critical energy is reached, the crack will overcome the resistance of z-pins and grow faster with the z-pins being pulled-out [4]. Meanwhile the load will drop abruptly. Corresponding crack lengths have been added to Fig. 6 which recaptures this fracture process. Although the composites without z-pins have shown zigzag phenomenon, the z-pinned ones act more severely and “bang jumps” are observed, in whose condition the crack propagates unstably until the redundant released strain energy has been consumed by the newly-built free surfaces or arrested by the next

z-pins in the way. Moreover, finite element method (FEM) using the cohesive element [11,12] in Fig. 7 shows the crack-affected area, which is about 3.4 mm in front of the crack tip. The crack-affected area proves that the z-pins encountered directly to the crack are supported by their back companions and otherwise they have to fight against delamination only with the resin matrix.

Fig. 6. Loading curves with crack lengths (a) RMD samples (b) STP samples. Note that green dots mean that crack tip has arrived at the scaling line but has not propagated yet.

Fig. 7. FEM results showing the crack-affected area behind crack tip. Note that sample thickness is 4 mm with the z-pins column distance of 2 mm.

Different from the unpinned samples, G_{Ic} of the z-pinned MBWK fabric/epoxy ones show a more fluctuating trend with the crack length, which is due to the resistance of z-pins to the crack propagation and can also be found elsewhere [4,9]. As a strong but not homogeneous bridging, z-pins can not only raise G_{Ic} remarkably (about 2.5 times herein) compared with the unpinned composites but also make G_{Ic} drop abruptly or jump wildly sometimes between the wide span of the neighbouring z-pins columns as shown in Fig. 4. Since z-pin fracture is seldom observed in quasi-static Mode I delamination tests [13], the stress field in the wake of the crack front and the pin/matrix interfacial properties will determine the fracture behaviour of the composites. It is clear that in this study the z-pins pull-out procedure, which is initiated by the z-pin debonding and which accompanies the crack growth, is not a balanced one in which the energy releases slowly. Furthermore, sometimes two columns of z-pins lose their delamination resistance capacities at the same time, which makes things worse, as shown in Fig. 4.

Combine Fig. 4 and Fig. 6. For the RMD samples, before the crack tip arrives at 76.5 mm, the crack growth behaviour does not show obviously difference from the unpinned ones. However, a “bang jump” happens suddenly at 76.5 mm, as a result of which two columns of z-pins are pulled-out at one short time and the G_{Ic} for the residual z-pins can no longer be as high as before due to the interface damage. For the STP samples, the two z-pins cooperate with the first column of z-pins at the beginning, absorb some released energy from the pull-out of the front-line z-pins and protect the following three z-pins from possible debonding. However, the crack loses its mild temper after the second peak load where the crack length has reached 67 mm. From the loading curve it is clear that during this sub-process, so much strain energy has been aggregated that the sudden release of these energy along the crack path induces high-rate stress by means of locally instable propagation. Even the five z-pins column at 77 mm cannot win the sudden attack from the crack that the crack tip successfully damages the interphase and passes by. Then a new pull-out sub-process begins on these five z-pins and energy is re-aggregated for the DCB until the third peak is formed. Since the last five z-pins at 88 mm are free from previously interfacial damage, a high G_{Ic} value is found at 89.5 mm, part of which comes from the contribution of the z-pins standing behind them.

Z-PINS TOPOLOGY DESIGN

Mutual Distance Criteria

Z-pins topology design is an attempt to get better performance of composite structures with a given number of z-pins within a given area, which is in fact a very complicated problem from whether energy or stress points of views. From the energy point, existence of z-pins increases the stiffness of the DCBs and consumes energy by being pulled-out, which can be depicted by the strain energy release rate G_{Ic} . While from the stress point, existence of z-pins changes the stress field in the wake of the delamination front, which can be expressed by the stress intensity factor K_{Ic} and more complicated than the energy view. And, what's more, if the “bang jumps” happen, the bonding damage and degradation of the z-pins near the front ones are very difficult to be

incorporated in both methods. Herein a few Criteria, named mutual distance Criteria (MDC), based on the experimental observations are proposed, which may be helpful to further analyses.

Fig. 8. Resin pocket in the MBWK fabric/epoxy composite.

Fig. 9. Bending failure of the z-pinned composites due to strength deficiency.

Resin pockets shall be minimized and especially resin channel shall be avoided (MDC-1). Resin pockets in the composites have been reported by many others [3] and are severer in unidirectional laminates than cross-ply ones. For the MBWK fabrics (Fig. 8), since z-pins are inserted in the space among the insertion GFs and along the PET stitch yarns, the minimum distance between two neighbouring z-pins have been bounded as 2.12 mm due to the fabric parameters in Table 1. This criterion reflects the requirement of the micro-structures.

Bending failure shall coordinate with the delamination (MDC-2). As reported by Mouritz [3], composite strength reduces linearly as a function of z-pins volume fraction. Local increase of z-pins fractions can cause bending failure instead of delamination as shown in Fig. 9. In order to get as higher delamination resistance as possible for some parts of the structures inclined to suffer delamination, more z-pins will be inserted in this local area. However, at the same time, it may fail due to the strength deficiency. The best way to harmonize this dilemma is to use an adequate number of z-pins with special topology. Mutual distance of the z-pins shall be chosen elaborately to minimize the reduction of strength.

Subsequent support of the front z-pins shall be considered (MDC-3). Considering the mechanisms of the z-pin pull-out (Fig. 10) [14] and Mode I delamination tests [4], the support consists of three types. The first one is involved in the elastic deformation stage of the front z-pins by affecting the stress field to decrease the stress concentration, which requires the subsequent ones standing in the crack-affected area of the front ones. The second one is to slow down the debonding and friction processes of the front

sacrificed z-pins. Obviously if these processes take place in a calm way, no “bang jumps” will occur. The third one is to absorb the suddenly released energy by the subsequent z-pins if “bang jumps” happens, which can protect the farther z-pins from high-rate stress loading to ensure their static-loading-resistance ability. This type requires the subsequent z-pins existing farther than the first two ones.

In general, the three Criteria above bound the mutual distance of the z-pins. The first two Criteria offer the minimum distance while the last one proposes the maximum bound. Neither too near nor too far is preferable z-pins mutual distance.

Fig. 10. Pull-out test of 9 z-pins. Note that the values of load and displacement vary with the z-pins diameter and length in the sample.

Fig. 11. Z-pinned composites delamination process.

A Conceptual Case Study

Now we return to the RMD and STP designs in this study. Suppose the z-pins follow the same rule with the pull-out tests in Fig. 10 during the Mode I delamination process. The conceptual case study is shown in Fig. 11. The z-pins pull-out displacement δ is a function of the crack growth Δa expressed as

$$\delta = \delta(\Delta a) \quad (2)$$

which can be determined by the Timoshenko’s beam theory or FEM taking the z-pins bridging stresses [7,10,15] into account. The mutual distance a_p , the design objective, will be included in the δ - Δa relation. Note that herein the z-pin numbers in every column are not necessarily equal to realize the topology scheme. In order to have stable crack propagation, $d\delta/dt$ or $d(\Delta a)/dt$ should be restricted to a small value and furthermore $d^2\delta/dt^2$ or $d^2(\Delta a)/dt^2$ should not be large.

When the z-pinned composites delaminate, the energy release rate contributed by the z-pins G_{lc}^P can be derived from the pull-out tests as below,

$$G_{lc}^P = \frac{1}{\Delta a \cdot B} \int_0^\delta P^P d\delta = G_{lc}^P(\delta) \quad (3)$$

where P^P is the load in the pull-out test. Define the energy release rate contributed by the newly-built surface as G_{lc}^N , which is regarded as the one derived from the un-pinned composites, then the total energy release rate will be

$$G_{lc}^T = G_{lc}^P + G_{lc}^N \quad (4)$$

And the energy equilibrium equation will be

$$\int_0^D PdD = \Delta a \cdot B \cdot G_{lc}^T + B \int_0^H \int_0^{a+\Delta a} (\sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \tau_{xy} \gamma_{xy}) dx dz \quad (5)$$

where H is the thickness of one arm of the DCB. The three terms in Eq. 4 mean the total external work, the released strain energy and the stored strain energy after the crack growth, respectively. Consider loading rate in the delamination tests. The left side of Eq. 5 will include the time term and the crack growth can be regarded as stable propagation if the growth rate is comparable to the loading rate. Eqs. 2 to 5 propose an analytical method to study the topology effects on the Mode I delamination.

CONCLUSIONS

The MBWK fabric/epoxy composites have been manufactured for the purpose of z-pins topology effects on the Mode I delamination properties. The strain energy release rate of the z-pinned composites is about 2.5 times that of un-pinned composites. Different from the unpinned samples whose G_{lc} value is constant when the crack length is large or the crack propagation is stable, the z-pinned MBWK fabric/epoxy composites show a more fluctuating trend of G_{lc} with the crack length, which is due to the resistance of z-pins to the crack propagation. Z-pins topology may have some effects on the delamination resistance.

Based on the Mode I delamination tests of the regular matrix-like distribution and the

spatial topology pattern of z-pins, three topology design Criteria are summarized from the view points of micro-structure, bending strength and subsequent support. Furthermore, a conceptual case study scheme is proposed to design the z-pins topology theoretically or numerically. It is believed that in future engineering designs of the composite structures, by particularly locating z-pins the material performance may be optimized with a fixed number of z-pins.

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